

Dr. Dennis Henkel

Physician | Medical Historian | Researcher at the University of Cologne

Short Profile

Dennis Henkel is a German physician, medical historian, and researcher at the University of Cologne. His work is situated at the intersection of psychiatry, the history and ethics of medicine, medical humanities, and film studies. A particular focus of his research lies on representations of medicine, psychiatry, disease, and ethical conflict in film, especially in early cinema and the silent era.

Alongside his clinical work, he has developed a distinctive academic profile through monographs, edited volumes, peer-reviewed journal articles, invited talks, and interdisciplinary teaching. In 2025, he completed his habilitation and received the *venia legendi* in the history and ethics of medicine at the University of Cologne.

Current Academic Position

- Physician
 - Research associate at the **Institute for the History and Ethics of Medicine, University of Cologne**
 - **Privatdozent (*venia legendi*) in the History and Ethics of Medicine, University of Cologne (2025)**
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Research Interests

- Psychiatry and film
- History and ethics of medicine
- Medical humanities

- Medicine and disease in early cinema
 - Dementia, trauma, addiction, and suicide in film
 - Gendered representations of psychiatrists and physicians in cinema
 - Medical ethics in film and visual culture
 - Cultural history of neurology and psychiatry
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Academic Profile

Dennis Henkel's research combines clinical psychiatric experience with medical-historical and film-historical analysis. His work explores how cinema has shaped perceptions of physicians, psychiatrists, patients, disease, addiction, trauma, dementia, and ethical conflict. He has published on topics such as addiction and drugs in silent cinema, dementia in film, infectious disease narratives, the image of psychiatry in film, and the historical representation of surgery, neurology, and medical institutions on screen.

A recurring focus of his work is the use of film as a source for the history of medicine and psychiatry. His publications engage with both scholarly and public debates and connect historical analysis with contemporary ethical and clinical questions. His ongoing work also includes further edited volumes as well as invited contributions in medical history and clinical ethics.

Selected Books

- **Silent Craving: Sucht und Drogen im Stummfilm (1890–1931)**
Kassel University Press, 2019.
- **Medizin und Krankheit im frühen Kino. Eine Erschließung des Stummfilms als primär-medizinhistorische Quelle**
Springer, 2025.
- **Demenz im Film. Wie das Kino vergessen lernte (ed.)**
Springer, 2023.
- **Seuchen, Epidemien und Pandemien im Film. Ein kaleidoskopisches Panorama zur Geschichte des Infektionsfilms (co-ed., first editor)**
Waxmann, 2022.

Forthcoming Editorial Projects

- **Gewalt, Verlust, Verletzung: Trauma und Traumatisierung im Film (ed.)**
Springer, forthcoming.

- **Depression im Film** (ed.)
Springer, forthcoming.
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Selected Journal Publications

- **The subverted film tropes of dementia**
The Lancet Neurology, 2026.
 - **Demenz im Kino – Enttabuisierung auf Kosten der Authentizität?**
Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift, 2025.
 - **Psychiaterinnen im Film: Ursprung und Entwicklung eines genderspezifischen Figurenstereotyps (1935–2020)**
Der Nervenarzt, 2025.
 - **The two sides of the scalpel: The polarizing image of surgery in early cinema**
PLOS ONE, 2022.
 - **Cinema's Terrifying Realities: Pandemics, Zombification, and SARS-CoV-2**
Clinical Medicine & Research, 2022.
 - **Not just escapism: Medicine-related fiction films as therapeutical and education tools amid pandemic**
Revista de Medicina y Cine, 2022.
 - **Medicine on the big and small screen: The portrayal of medicine in silent fiction films**
Pharos, 2020.
 - **Nicht nur Slapstick: Stummfilme als unterschätzte Zeugen der Medizingeschichte**
Deutsche Medizinische Wochenschrift, 2020.
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Teaching

Dennis Henkel regularly teaches in the history and ethics of medicine, medical humanities, and clinical ethics. His teaching includes courses and seminars on psychiatry in film, dementia, medical terminology, ethical questions in medicine, and the use of film in medical and interdisciplinary teaching. He has also contributed to teaching in dentistry and midwifery studies.

Selected International Talks

- **European Psychiatric Association (EPA), Madrid**

- **International Society for the History of the Neurosciences (ISHN), Rennes and Paris**
- **World Congress for Psychotherapy, Vienna**

His invited talks address themes such as psychosis and delusion in film, neurology in early cinema, dementia in film, and the history of psychiatry and medicine in visual culture.

Media and Public Engagement

Dennis Henkel's work has received attention in both academic and public contexts, including:

- a **Deutschlandfunk** interview on dementia in film,
 - public and professional events on **assisted suicide in film**,
 - academic reviews and coverage in film- and media-related forums,
 - and lectures connecting psychiatry, ethics, medicine, and cinema.
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Institutional Affiliation

Institute for the History and Ethics of Medicine
University of Cologne
Cologne, Germany

Links

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Google Scholar: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=dKxQ_a8AAAAJ

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/dr-dennis-henkel-33300039b/>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Dennis-Henkel>

Contact

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